

Synthesis, spectral and physicochemical studies of Co^{II}, Ni^{II} and Cu^{II} complexes with thiosemicarbazone (L¹) and semicarbazone (L²) derived from 2-acetyl thiophene

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Abstract : Co^{II}, Ni^{II} and Cu^{II} complexes are synthesized with thiosemicarbazone (L¹) and semicarbazone (L²) derived from 2-acetyl thiophene. These complexes are characterized by elemental analysis, molar conductance, magnetic susceptibility measurements, mass, IR, electronic and EPR spectral studies. The molar conductance measurements of the complexes in DMSO correspond to non electrolytic nature except Co(L²)₂(NO₃)₂ complex which is 1 : 2 electrolyte. All the complexes are of high-spin type. On the basis of spectral studies an octahedral geometry may be assigned for Co^{II} and Ni^{II} complexes except Co(L²)(NO₃)₂ complex which is of tetrahedral geometry. A tetragonal geometry may be assigned for Cu^{II} complexes.

Keywords : Spectral studies, thiosemicarbazone, semicarbazone, 2-acetyl thiophene.

Thiosemicarbazones usually act as chelating ligands with transition metal ion, bonding through the sulphur and hydrazine nitrogen atom. Thiosemicarbazones and their complexes have received considerable attention because of their pharmacological properties¹. The metal complexes show more activities as compared to the free thiosemicarbazones and semicarbazones. They may have numerous applications e.g. anticancer², fungicides, antibacterial^{3,4}, antiviral^{5,6}, antifungal^{7,8}, anti HIV⁹, antitumour¹⁰ and other biological activities¹¹⁻¹³. Particularly first row of transition metal complexes with such ligands have a wide range of biological activities¹⁴⁻¹⁸.

In view of the above applications it is highly desirable to synthesize and characterize transition metal complexes with such ligands. In the present paper we report the synthesis and characterization of complexes with thiosemicarbazone (L¹) and semicarbazone (L²) derived from 2-acetyl thiophene.

Experimental

All the chemicals used were of analytical grade and procured from Sigma Aldrich. Metal salts were purchased from E. Merck and were used as received.

Y = S, for L¹

Y = O, for L²

Fig. 1. Structure of ligands.

Preparation of ligands : Ligands L¹ and L² were prepared and the methods of their preparation are given below.

Ligand L¹ : Hot ethanolic solution (20 mL) of 2-acetyl thiophene (1.26 g, 0.01 mol) was mixed with hot ethanolic solution of thiosemicarbazide (0.95 g, 0.01 mol). The contents were refluxed for about 2-3 h on a water bath. On cooling the contents the white colored compound is separated out. The same was filtered, washed with 50% ethanol and dried in vacuum over P₄O₁₀. Yield 70%, m.p. 159-161 °C (Found : C, 42.4; H, 4.8; N, 21.4. Calcd. for C₆H₉N₃S₂ (molecular mass 199 amu) : C, 42.1; H, 4.5; N, 21.08%).

Ligand L² : An aqueous solution (20 mL) of semicarbazone HCl (1.11 g, 0.01 mol) was added to a ethanolic solution (20 mL) of 2-acetyl thiophene (1.26 g, 0.01 mol) in the presence of sodium acetate (1.36 g, 0.01 mol). The reaction mixture was stirred vigorously for around an hour. The crystalline light yellow product which formed was collected by filtration, washed several times with hot water and dried in vacuum over P₄O₁₀. Yield 73%, m.p. 195–197 °C (Found : C, 46.0; H, 4.7; N, 22.6. Calcd. for C₇H₉N₃OS (molecular mass 183 amu) : C, 45.8; H, 4.9; N, 22.9%).

Synthesis of complexes : A hot ethanolic solution (20 mL) of corresponding metal salts (0.005 mol for each case) was mixed with hot ethanolic solution of the respective ligand (0.01 mol) and refluxed for 3–4 h on a water bath. On cooling the contents, the colored complex separated out in each case. The same was filtered, washed with 50% ethanol and dried in vacuum over P₄O₁₀. Purity of the complexes was checked by TLC.

Physical measurements : The C, H, N were analyzed on a Carlo-Erba 1106 elemental analyzer. Molar conductance was measured on the Eleco (CM82T) conducting bridge. Magnetic susceptibility was measured at room temperature on a Gouy balance using CuSO₄·5H₂O as a calibrant. Mass spectra were recorded on JEOL, JMS.DX-303 mass spectrometer. IR spectra (KBr) were recorded on a FTIR spectrum BX-II spectrophotometer. The electronic spectra were recorded in DMSO on Shimadzu UV mini-1240 spectrophotometer. EPR spectra of the complexes were recorded as polycrystalline sample at LNT for Co^{II} complexes and at room temperature for Cu^{II} complexes on E4-EPR spectrometer using DPPH as the g-marker.

Results and discussion

Ligand L¹ : The IR spectrum of L¹ shows bands at 3380 and 3171 cm⁻¹ which may be, assigned to -NH₂ and -NH groups respectively. The bands due to ν(C=S) and ν(C=N) groups appeared at 1107 and 1597 cm⁻¹. The mass spectrum of free ligand L¹ confirms the proposed formula by showing a peak at 200 amu corresponding to the molecular ion (M⁺ + 1) C₇H₉N₃S₂. It also shows a peak corresponding to loss of (-CSNH₂) i.e. at 140 amu and various other fragments (Fig. 2).

Ligand L² : The IR spectrum of ligand L² shows bands at 3380 and 3171 cm⁻¹ which may be assigned to -NH₂ and -NH group respectively. The band ν(C=N) appeared at 1601 cm⁻¹. The mass spectrum of free ligand L² confirm the proposed formula by showing a peak at 184 amu corresponding to the molecular ion (M⁺ + 1) C₇H₉N₃OS. It also shows a peak corresponding to loss of (-CONH₂) i.e. at 140 amu and various other fragments (Fig. 3).

Complexes : On complexation the bands corresponding to ν(C=N) and ν(C=S) (in case of thiosemicarbazide) shifted towards lower side (around ca. 20–30 cm⁻¹) suggest that the ligand acts as a bidentate chelating agent coordinating through nitrogen of ν(C=N) group and sulphur of ν(C=S) group. In case semicarbazones the bands of ν(C=N) and the band of ν(C=O) shifted towards lower side (around ca. 20–30 cm⁻¹) suggests that the ligand also acts as bidentate chelating agent coordinating through nitrogen of ν(C=N) group and oxygen of ν(C=O) group.

Fig. 2. Mass spectrum of the ligand L¹.

Fig. 3. Mass spectrum of the ligand L^2

On the basis of elemental analysis the complexes were found to have the composition as shown in Table 1. The molar conductance measurements of the complexes in DMSO correspond to non electrolytic nature¹⁹ except $\text{Co}(L^2)_2(\text{NO}_3)_2$ complex which is 1 : 2 electrolytes. Thus the complexes may be formulated as $[\text{M}(L)_2X_2]$ where $\text{M} = \text{Cu}^{\text{II}}, \text{Co}^{\text{II}}$ and Ni^{II} and $\text{X} = \text{Cl}^-$ and NO_3^- [$\text{L} = L^1$ and L^2] and $[\text{Co}(L^2)_2](\text{NO}_3)_2$.

IR spectra of nitrate complexes of $\text{Co}(L^2)_2(\text{NO}_3)_2$ show sharp and strong band at 1384 cm^{-1} indicate that the nitrate group is uncoordinated. IR spectra of nitrate complexes of Ni^{II} display three absorption bands at 1418–1427, 1303–1311 and $1003\text{--}1012 \text{ cm}^{-1}$ suggesting that both the nitrate groups are coordinated to the metal ion²⁰⁻²³.

Copper(II) complexes : Magnetic moment of all the Cu^{II} complexes at room temperature lie in the range 1.98–2.07 B.M. corresponding to one unpaired electron (Table 2). The electronic spectra of six coordinated Cu^{2+} complexes have either D_{4h} or C_{4v} symmetry and the E_g and T_{2g} levels of the 2D free ion term will split into $B_{1g}, A_{1g},$

B_{2g}, E_g levels respectively. Thus three-spin allowed transition are expected in the visible and near IR region. But only a few complexes are known in which such bands are resolved either by “Gaussian Analysis” or by “Single crystal polarization” studies. These Cu^{II} complexes under study give rise absorption spectral band in the range $13000\text{--}16000$ and $16000\text{--}20000 \text{ cm}^{-1}$. These bands have been assigned to the following transition in order of increasing energy^{24,25}.

EPR spectra of Cu^{II} complexes were recorded as polycrystalline sample on X-band at frequency 9.5 GHz under the magnetic field strength 3400 Gauss. All the complexes show anisotropic EPR spectra²⁶. The g values have been calculated by Kneubuhl’s method³². $G = (g_{\text{II}} - 2)/(g_{\text{I}} - 2)$, which measures the exchange interaction between copper centers in the polycrystalline solid. According to Hathaway^{27,28} if the value of G is above four then exchange interaction is negligible, if however the value of G is less than four it indicates considerable exchange interaction in the solid complexes. In the complexes reported here the G value is less than 4 indicating the exchange interaction in solid complexes.

Table 1. Elemental analysis and molar conductance data of complexes

Complex	Mol. cond. ($\Omega^{-1} \text{ cm}^2 \text{ mol}^{-1}$)	Color	M.p. ($^{\circ}\text{C}$)	Yield (%)	Elemental analysis (%) : Found (Calcd.)			
					M	C	H	N
$\text{Co}(\text{L}^1)_2\text{Cl}_2$	15	Dark brown	188	66	11.40 (11.16)	31.58 (31.82)	3.17 (3.40)	15.71 (15.91)
$\text{Co}(\text{L}^1)_2(\text{NO}_3)_2$	10	Rose pink	182	61	10.37 (10.14)	28.68 (28.91)	3.34 (3.09)	19.03 (19.27)
$\text{Co}(\text{L}^2)_2\text{Cl}_2$	11	Purple	230	62	11.68 (11.88)	33.55 (33.80)	3.40 (3.62)	16.70 (16.93)
$\text{Co}(\text{L}^2)_2(\text{NO}_3)_2$	183	Tobacco brown	233	60	10.50 (10.73)	30.38 (30.60)	3.52 (3.22)	20.60 (20.40)
$\text{Ni}(\text{L}^1)_2\text{Cl}_2$	10	Green	187	65	11.36 (11.12)	40.70 (40.93)	3.64 (3.48)	15.67 (15.91)
$\text{Ni}(\text{L}^1)_2(\text{NO}_3)_2$	156	Magenta	185	67	10.36 (10.11)	37.33 (37.19)	3.34 (3.09)	19.50 (19.28)
$\text{Ni}(\text{L}^2)_2\text{Cl}_2$	12	Cream yellow	220	57	11.63 (11.84)	33.58 (33.80)	3.26 (3.02)	16.71 (16.94)
$\text{Ni}(\text{L}^2)_2(\text{NO}_3)_2$	160	Brown	232	62	10.48 (10.69)	30.42 (30.60)	3.02 (3.28)	20.64 (20.41)
$\text{Cu}(\text{L}^1)_2\text{Cl}_2$	23	Green	190	61	11.72 (11.93)	31.32 (31.54)	3.13 (3.38)	15.53 (15.77)
$\text{Cu}(\text{L}^1)_2(\text{NO}_3)_2$	19	Brown	185	66	10.67 (10.85)	28.51 (28.69)	3.32 (3.07)	19.36 (19.12)
$\text{Cu}(\text{L}^2)_2\text{Cl}_2$	24	Light green	223	61	12.47 (12.69)	33.33 (33.50)	3.35 (3.59)	16.50 (16.78)
$\text{Cu}(\text{L}^2)_2(\text{NO}_3)_2$	165	Pale brown	227	60	11.67 (11.47)	30.53 (30.30)	3.01 (3.25)	20.48 (20.23)

Nickel(II) complexes : The value of magnetic moments for the complexes under study lies in the range from 2.93–3.04 B.M. (Table 2). The electronic spectra of the Ni^{II} complexes show bands in the range 8580–13000, 11000–20000 and 19000–27000 cm^{-1} corresponding to spin allowed transitions ${}^3A_{2g}(F) \rightarrow {}^3T_{2g}$, ${}^3A_{2g}(F) \rightarrow {}^3T_{1g}(F)$, ${}^3A_{2g}(P) \rightarrow {}^3T_{1g}(P)$ indicate an octahedral geometry.

Cobalt(II) complexes : All the complexes under study show the magnetic moment in the range 4.76–4.86 B.M. (Table 2) corresponding to three unpaired electrons. Under study Co^{II} complexes (except nitrate complex with L^2) display electronic spectral bands in the range of 7000–10000, 14000–17000 and 18000–22000 cm^{-1} . These may be assigned to the following transitions. ${}^4T_{1g}(F) \rightarrow {}^4T_{2g}(F)$, ${}^4T_{1g}(F) \rightarrow {}^4A_{2g}(F)$, ${}^4T_{1g}(F) \rightarrow {}^4T_{1g}(P)$ characteristic to an octahedral geometry whereas the nitrate complex of Co^{II} with L^2 show three electronic spectral bands

Table 2. Magnetic moment (B.M.) and electronic spectral data (cm^{-1}) of complexes

Complex	μ_{eff} (B.M.)	Electronic spectral data		
		ν_1	ν_2	ν_3
$\text{Co}(\text{L}^1)_2\text{Cl}_2$	4.80	9420	14525	18975
$\text{Co}(\text{L}^1)_2(\text{NO}_3)_2$	4.83	9325	14450	18775
$\text{Co}(\text{L}^2)_2\text{Cl}_2$	4.76	9509	14505	21380
$\text{Co}(\text{L}^2)_2(\text{NO}_3)_2$	4.86	5810	14620	21570
$\text{Ni}(\text{L}^1)_2\text{Cl}_2$	2.97	9680	16200	24500
$\text{Ni}(\text{L}^1)_2(\text{NO}_3)_2$	2.93	9650	15250	24600
$\text{Ni}(\text{L}^2)_2\text{Cl}_2$	3.04	9790	14925	24790
$\text{Ni}(\text{L}^2)_2(\text{NO}_3)_2$	2.97	7800	13650	24650
$\text{Cu}(\text{L}^1)_2\text{Cl}_2$	2.06	14580	16675	–
$\text{Cu}(\text{L}^1)_2(\text{NO}_3)_2$	2.03	13214	16540	–
$\text{Cu}(\text{L}^2)_2\text{Cl}_2$	2.07	13640	16500	–
$\text{Cu}(\text{L}^2)_2(\text{NO}_3)_2$	1.98	15700	19525	–

around 5000, 8000 and 19000 cm^{-1} corresponding to the following transitions indicate tetrahedral geometry.

The 4F state of d^7 in an octahedral crystal field is split into three states. Since these states are connected by the spin orbit coupling the spin lattice relaxation times are short making EPR measurements possible only at very low temperature. EPR spectra of the complexes recorded as polycrystalline sample at liquid nitrogen temperature and g values are given in Table 3.

Table 3. Ligand field parameter and g value of complexes

Complex	g	LFSE (kJ mol^{-1})	Dq (cm^{-1})	β
$\text{Co}(\text{L}^1)_2\text{Cl}_2$	1.79	135	942	0.55
$\text{Co}(\text{L}^1)_2(\text{NO}_3)_2$	1.89	133	932	0.54
$\text{Co}(\text{L}^2)_2\text{Cl}_2$	1.79	136	950	0.86
$\text{Co}(\text{L}^2)_2(\text{NO}_3)_2$	1.77	83	581	0.87
$\text{Ni}(\text{L}^1)_2\text{Cl}_2$	-	139	968	0.74
$\text{Ni}(\text{L}^1)_2(\text{NO}_3)_2$	-	138	965	0.69
$\text{Ni}(\text{L}^2)_2\text{Cl}_2$	-	140	979	0.66
$\text{Ni}(\text{L}^2)_2(\text{NO}_3)_2$	-	112	780	0.95
$\text{Cu}(\text{L}^1)_2\text{Cl}_2$	2.00	-	-	-
$\text{Cu}(\text{L}^1)_2(\text{NO}_3)_2$	1.97	-	-	-
$\text{Cu}(\text{L}^2)_2\text{Cl}_2$	1.99	-	-	-
$\text{Cu}(\text{L}^2)_2(\text{NO}_3)_2$	1.89	-	-	-

Ligand field parameters : Various ligand parameters are calculated for the complexes. The value of Dq in Co^{II} complexes were calculated from transition energy ratio diagram using the ν_3/ν_2 ratio²⁹. The Nephelauxetic parameter β was readily obtained by using the relation $\beta = B(\text{complex})/B(\text{free ion})$, where B free ion for Ni^{II} is 1041 cm^{-1} and for Co^{II} is 1120 cm^{-1} ^{30,31}. The β lies in the range 0.54–0.95 (Table 3). These values indicate the appreciable covalent character of metal ligand σ bond.

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References

- N. K. Singh and A. Srivastava, *Transition Met. Chem.*, 2000, **25**, 133.
- Min Wang, Liu-Fang Wang, Yi-Zhi Ligands and Qin-Xi-Li, *Transition Met. Chem.*, 2001, **26**, 307.
- S. D. Dhumwad, K. B. Gudasi and T. R. Goudar, *Indian J. Chem., Sect. A*, 1994, **33**, 320.
- N. N. Gulerman, S. Rollas, H. Erdeniz and M. Kiraj, *J. Pharm. Sci.*, 2001, **26**, 1.
- K. H. Reddy, P. S. Reddy and P. R. Babu, *Transition Met. Chem.*, 2000, **25**, 154.
- P. Tarasconi, S. Capacchi, G. Pelosi, M. Cornia, R. Albertini, A. Bonati, P. P. Dall, P. Luunghi and S. Pinelli, *Bioorg. Med. Chem.*, 2000, **8**, 154.
- H. Singh, L. D. S. Yadav and S. B. S. Mishra, *J. Inorg. Nucl. Chem.*, 1981, **43**, 1701.
- D. X. West, S. L. Dietrich, I. Thiantanavanich, C. A. Brown and A. E. Liberta, *Transition Met. Chem.*, 1994, **19**, 320.
- N. K. Singh and S. B. Singh, *Indian J. Chem., Sect. A*, 2001, **40**, 1070.
- V. Mishra, S. N. Pandeya and S. Anathan, *Acta Pharm. Turc.*, 2000, **42**, 139.
- D. Jamal and M. A. Quaraishi, *J. Electrochem. Soc. India*, 2000, **49**, 56.
- E. M. Jouad, A. Riou, M. Allian, M. A. Khan and G. M. Bouet, *Polyhedron*, 2001, **20**, 67.
- Z. Xinde, C. Wang, Z. Lu and Y. Dang, *Transition Met. Chem.*, 1997, **22**, 13.
- S. Chandra and K. Gupta, *Transition Met. Chem.*, 2002, **27**, 196.
- A. M. Dhiman and K. N. Wododkar, *Indian J. Chem., Sect. A*, 2001, **40**, 636.
- S. Chandra and K. Gupta, *Transition Met. Chem.*, 2002, **27**, 329.
- W. G. Geary, *Coord. Chem. Rev.*, 1971, **7**, 81.
- C. R. K. Rao and P. S. Zacharias, *Polyhedron*, 1977, **16**, 1201; S. Chandra and L. K. Gupta, *Spectrochimica Acta (A)*, 2004, **60**, 3079.
- M. Shakir, S. P. Varkey and P. S. Hameed, *Polyhedron*, 1993, **12**, 2775; S. Chandra and L. K. Gupta, *Spectrochimica Acta (A)*, 2004, **60**, 2767.
- M. Shakir, O. S. M. Nasman, A. K. Mohamed and S. P. Varkey, *Indian J. Chem., Sect. A*, 1996, **35**, 710.
- K. Nakamoto, "Infrared and Raman Spectra of Coordination Compounds", Wiley Interscience, New York, 1970.
- A. B. P. Lever, "Inorganic Electronic Spectroscopy", 2nd ed., Elsevier, Amsterdam, 1984.
- V. V. Pavlishchuk, S. P. Kolotilov, A. W. Addison, R. J. Butche and E. Sinn, *J. Chem. Soc., Dalton Trans.*, 2000, 335.
- S. Chandra, K. Gupta and S. Sharma, *Synth. React. Inorg. Metal-Org. Chem.*, 2001, **31**, 1205.
- B. J. Hathaway and D. E. Billing, *Coord. Chem. Rev.*

- 1970, **6**, 143; B. J. Hathaway and R. J. Dudley, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1970, 1725.
26. R. S. Drago, "Physical Method in Chemistry", W. B. Saunders Company, London, 1977, 647.
27. A. B. P. Lever. "Crystal Field Spectra, Inorganic Electronic Spectroscopy", 1st ed., Elsevier, Amsterdam, 1968, 249.
28. R. R. Fenton, R. Gauci, P. C. Junk, L. F. Lindoy, R. C. Luckay, G. V. Meehan, J. R. Price, P. Turner and G. Wei, *J. Chem. Soc., Dalton Trans.*, 2002, 2185; C. C. Silviacarvalho, R. Delgado, M. G. V. Drew, V. Felix and B. J. Goodfellow, *J. Chem. Soc., Dalton Trans.*, 2003, 3172.
29. S. Chandra, L. K. Gupta and K. Gupta, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 2004, **81**, 833.
30. D. Kivelson and R. Neiman, *J. Chem. Phys.*, 1961, **35**, 149.
31. S. Chandra and Sangeetika, *Spectrochimica Acta(A)*, 2004, **60**, 147; L. Mishra, A. K. Singh and Y. Maeda, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 2005, **82**, 879.
32. S. Chandra, L. K. Gupta and K. K. Sharma, *J. Saudi Chem. Soc.*, 2005, **9**, 131; M. A. Akbar, H. A. Mirza, A. Monsur and M. Nizamuddin, *Polyhedron*, 2001, **20**, 1045.